

Trial by Trolley™

Developed by: Cyanide & Happiness, Explosm LLC, Skybound Games, and Lucky Duck Games

Article contributed by: Kevin Rebecchi

Keywords

Competition, Cooperation, Creativity, Critical Thinking, Empathy, Ethical Decision-making, Ethical Dilemmas, Philosophy, Psychosocial Skills, Rhetoric

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the trolley problem, the core dilemma of *Trial by Trolley™* (Cyanide & Happiness, Explosm LLC, Skybound Games, and Lucky Duck Games). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

Trial by Trolley™ is a social and ethical decision-making game developed and published by Cyanide & Happiness, Explosm LLC, Skybound Games, and Lucky Duck Games in 2019. The game is based on the well-known trolley problem (see Figure 1), a thought experiment in ethics that presents players with a moral dilemma: should they divert a runaway trolley to save one group of people at the expense of another?

While *Trial by Trolley* was not originally designed as an educational game, it can be effectively adapted for use in higher education, particularly in psychology, philosophy, ethics, education, law, and cognitive or social sciences. The game can serve as an engaging tool to help students develop critical thinking, argumentation skills, and ethical reasoning by evaluating complex moral choices. Moreover, it is highly relevant in the context of psychosocial skills (World Health Organization, 1994) training, which aims to enhance individuals' cognitive (self-awareness, self-control, constructive decision-making), emotional (the ability to understand, identify, and regulate one's emotions and stress), and social skills (constructive communication, relationship-building, and resolving difficulties) (Lamboy et al., 2022).

Facts

Release date:	first published in 2019, continually updated with new extensions
Developer:	Cyanide & Happiness, Explosm LLC, Skybound Games, and Lucky Duck Games
Game type:	Analog
Number of players:	3–13 (recommended for groups)
Format:	Synchronous, adaptable to classroom discussions
Time frame:	Each round, including setup and discussion, takes about 15–30 minutes, depending on the number of players and the type of dilemma
Languages:	English, German, French, Italian, Spanish, Dutch
Environment:	Physical board game or online adaptation
Material:	Base game available commercially
Price:	About 30€, but varies by retailer and country.

Resonance & Criticism

Trial by Trolley was funded through a Kickstarter campaign between 8 July and 8 August 2019. During this period, 55,024 contributors from around the world (including the United States, Canada, the United Kingdom, Australia, Germany, France, the Netherlands, Denmark, Sweden, and Spain) pledged a total of US\$3,538,065 to support the project. The game was launched in English but is now also available in German, French, Spanish, Italian, and Dutch.

This party game facilitates engaging, humorous discussions of moral dilemmas. The game's casual, accessible format can make it particularly effective at sparking student debates, encouraging them to analyze ethical problems from multiple perspectives.

However, the humorous, exaggerated nature of some scenarios may undermine the seriousness of ethical discussions. Teachers may need to create new situations and cards, and guide discussions carefully to ensure students engage critically rather than purely for entertainment.

Game Principle & Process

In Trial by Trolley, one player takes on the role of an “operator” who must decide (after the debate) which of two tracks the runaway trolley will take. The other players split into two teams, each advocating for one of the tracks.

These teams use randomly drawn cards to populate the tracks with individuals or scenarios — some morally compelling (e.g., “a scientist on the verge of curing cancer”, “a group of diplomats on the verge of concluding world peace”), some negative (e.g., “a person who always double-parks”, “the guru of a dangerous sect”) while others can affect players personally or emotionally (e.g. “your families”, “all the nurses on Earth”). Players then present arguments to the operator to influence their decision. Players must also place modifier cards

associated with any card on either track (e.g., “is about to meet his/her soulmate and fall in love”, “is one month away from finishing a machine that will put you out of work”).

Each team has to discuss the matter internally, then try to convince the operator not to choose their track for sending the trolley.

In an educational context, teachers can easily modify the game by adding personalized scenario cards tailored to the learning objectives, depending on students' level (e.g., first or fifth year of university studies) and their course/discipline (e.g., education, psychology, philosophy, law...).

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Trial by Trolley can be beneficial in courses related to philosophy and ethics by enabling students to explore ethical theories and moral reasoning; to psychology to analyze cognitive biases, decision-making, and empathy; to law by discussing legal responsibility and judicial ethics; to education Sciences by teaching conflict resolution and perspective-taking; and/or to Political Science and Public Policy to evaluate real-world policy decisions and ethics in artificial intelligence.

As mentioned earlier, the game is also valuable for teaching psychosocial skills, as defined by the WHO as “a person’s ability to cope effectively with the demands and challenges of daily life” and the “ability to maintain a state of psychological well-being and to demonstrate it through appropriate and positive behavior in their interactions with others, their culture and their environment” (World Health Organization, 1994). These skills include problem-solving, creative thinking, effective communication, self-awareness, stress management, decision-making, critical thinking, interpersonal skills, empathy for others, and emotional management.

By actively engaging students in formal and continuing education in these dilemmas, Trial by Trolley can help them develop reasoning skills, justify and criticize moral decisions, and understand the complexity of ethical choices in real-world settings.

Effectiveness

While empirical studies on the use of Trial by Trolley in education are currently limited and unpublished, anecdotal evidence from teachers suggests it may be highly effective in stimulating discussion, engaging students in ethical reasoning, and fostering creative problem-solving.

The game's humorous, interactive format reduces resistance to discussing complex topics that can sometimes arise in more formal teaching, as it allows students to explore moral dilemmas in a low-stakes environment.

The game can also reinforce debate and argumentation skills, particularly when students have to defend their positions based on ethical principles. Combined with structured reflection and debriefing sessions, Trial by Trolley can be an exciting game for highlighting current and future

ethical challenges (e.g., teachers can easily create cards and dilemmas on topics such as artificial intelligence, new technologies, and climate change).

Potentially Problematic Aspects

The first aspect to mention is that some situations in the game are exaggerated for comedic effect, which may reduce the depth of ethical analysis (e.g., cards about pop stars, reality TV stars, pets, and fictional characters). Secondly, some scenarios may address controversial or triggering topics (e.g., political opinions, cultural practices), and teachers should choose which cards to use in an academic setting. Finally, since the game involves convincing the operator, students might focus on rhetorical strategies rather than genuine ethical analysis. It is therefore essential for teachers to encourage students to discuss the game situations afterwards, rather than treating the game as a self-contained educational tool.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl

Sources

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